

Systematic Review of Privacy Preservation Techniques in Big Data Analytics

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15751400

ABSTRACT

The huge amount of data that is being generated over the network is termed as Big Data. Big data involves collecting data from each and every field and systematically storing that. This data comes in every form that may be structured or unstructured like images, videos, text, etc. This all data can be used to extract information, for example, the text mining. The data present need to be preserved because of the privacy threats. The field of preserving the data in this field is called privacy preservation in big data and there are various techniques seen for this task. Here we are providing a review on the various privacy preservation techniques such as cosine similarity, K-anonymity, T-closeness, randomization, data distribution, L-diversity, cryptography and map-reduce method. We have studied all these techniques and the comparison among them was done here. The review paper studied that the K-Anonymity technique is more efficient and secure for privacy preservation in big data.

Keyword : - Big Data, Privacy Preservation Techniques, Data Privacy, K-anonymity, Generalization, Diversity.

1. INTRODUCTION

It has seen that the data is being produced in enormous amounts because of the variety of applications that are being used on the internet. Every field is producing a huge amount of data, this data varies with the field. The computer technology that reached up to every human being resulted in the production of data in such a manner [1]. The services provided by computer technology for the storage, processing, UI has become the reason for the growth of the data. This data may be available publically or some sensitive data that can be stored privately. The people provide their data on the internet as per the requirement. The data that does not affect the privacy of the person is available publically, whereas the data that contains personal data of the users and this data may have a threat to the security of the personal information is kept privately [2]. The data such as caste, shopping cart, gender, religion is some of the sensitive information.

This data is shared with the third party for the analysis of the data. These companies get the information of the users' data and find out the patterns that are seen in their data. This helps companies or websites to do the required changes along with the decisions to be taken for better service providing. The recommendation, prediction, forecasting are also important fields where this data is being used. In this all the recommendation system is the most important field where this data is analyzed by most of the leading websites like Flipkart, amazon, snapdeal etc for a product recommendation, apart from this there are many applications where the recommendations are made like a movie, tourist, friend recommendation etc [3].

But the revealing of this data may lead to security threats. SO, there is a need to define the privacy of the user's data and the privacy preservation should be implemented. There are a number of privacy preservation methods that are defined earlier to provide privacy to the user's data. All privacy preservation techniques have some advantages and also some limitations with drawbacks. So here we have provided a survey on these privacy preservation techniques and studied each technique in deep detail to provide a better survey. We have compared the privacy preservation methods on their implementation basis.

Big data is one of the fields where a large amount of data is analyzed. Big data is different as compared with the traditional technologies on the following basis: the volume, the variety, velocity and the value of data. The analysis of this big data is done for various purposes. The sales analysis and prediction of demands. As being so valuable this data also deals with privacy issues like cyber attacks, threats and frauds. The traditional technologies suffer from the privacy preservation of the data that is transferred and used on the internet. The cybercriminals can attack this data of

the users and the data can be stolen or it can get corrupted. Big data analytics is used by major agencies like NSA of the U.S. for getting terrorist activities. So, big data is having a crucial use in various fields but at the same time, the concerns about security and privacy are seen on top. Privacy-preserving is one of the biggest challenges in the big data field.

2. BACKGROUND STUDY

Here we have studied various aspects of the concerns of the big data applications in the security aspect as well as for the privacy of the communication system. The background study is defined in two ways:

The first one comes with the security aspects in big data analytics. Here we have studied the application of the big data in the improvement of the information security. Majorly the big data tools are used for the analysis of the data and for finding out the patterns of the data. Another domain is to analyze the frauds and the anomalies in the insurance sector, online banking, medical sector etc. The advance technology of big data which relates to the Hadoop where the live streaming data is analyzed. And The security analytics is done by the collection of information at huge scale, the analysis was done on this data and the view for the security of information and providing the live streaming of the data. The Big data tools for security requires professional analysts to do these tasks.

The next task is of the privacy issues of the BDA, as with the growth of the BDA there is the formation of newer issues for the privacy concerns. The privacy concerns such as the anonymization would not be possible, inaccuracy of BDA, there is need of the legal protection, discrimination, actions that are not authenticated for the interpretations, the masking of data may be broken for getting the information, the security of the information is also a big issue, there will be concerns related to the e-discovery, the patents and the copyright will become irrelevant. The BDA for the task of the concerns related to privacy is having many significant innovations and will be beneficial for every organization. So those ones who are going for the BDA with their organizational data must measure the security and the privacy concerns related to the BDA and their data.

2.1 Big Data: Big data can be understood as both the structured and unstructured data that is forming or present on the internet. It is present in an enormous amount from every field like a social network, e-commerce, real estate etc. But the big data itself is important for the analysis and the patterns present there in the data to find out [4]. The importance of big data comes only after the analysis of the data, this analysis helps in various applications such as recommendation, prediction, forecasting etc. The big data is majorly working on the three concepts that are 3V's.

Volume: The collection of data is done from various fields such as the transactions of business, IoT devices, social media etc. Previously it was difficult for the storing but presently it has become easy to store the volume of data.

Velocity: The use of social media and the internet nowadays have speeded up the production of data on the internet. The streaming of data must be handled promptly.

Variety: The data comes from every field so the variety is seen in the data that is being produced. The variety is seen as the formats of the data that are structured or unstructured both.

Value: This is one of the most important characteristics of big data that states the value of the data available. The value characteristic states the ability of the transformation of huge amount of data in the user data. This makes the data useful for business.

Veracity: This characteristic of big data deals with the quality of data. This characteristic of big data states that not only the data availability is important, but the data should be clean and accurate for storage and for the use.

2.2 Privacy Preservation in Big Data: Privacy comes at the top when someone shares his personal data on the internet [5]. And providing privacy to the customer is the ability of the service provider that the data can not be shared among any of the third-party applications. The overall control of the user's private data remains up to the specific website only. When the availability of the data is seen on the public platform then this data can be shared by many data holders [6]. Also, the transferring of such data over the internet also needs to be secured via privacy-preserving policy. This privacy to the user should be provided by the data holder itself [7].

When the data is transferred or the communication of data takes place in between the computers or websites the security must be provided as the data can not be shared for the third party and the data must remain between the communicating parties [8]. So, to provide privacy to the user's data many techniques can be applied to the data. Some of the techniques of privacy preservation are discussed in this paper like t-closeness, cosine similarity, cryptography, map-reduce etc.

Figure1. Big Data from various fields [4]

Figure2. Privacy preservation in Big Data [8]

2.3 Cloud Secure Alliance: The CSA is a service that provides security to the cloud computing environment. And is it an organization in which they have created a working group for big data [18]. This system has classified the various security and the privacy concerns that are seen in 4 aspects of the ecosystem of the big data. These four aspects are Infrastructure Security, Data Privacy, Data management and integrity and the last one as Reactive Security. The security concerns for the infrastructure is seen as it requires 1. Security in the data processing at distributed platforms, 2. The actions for the security for a database that is non-relational in nature. The Data Privacy aspect deals with the problems as 3. The preservation of the privacy of the data when we work on the data analysis from the data mining, 4. The data security by the cryptography, 5. Access control by granular manner. The third aspect as data management and integrity suffers the problem as a6. The security for the transaction log and the storage of data, 7. Granular audit, 8. Data provenance. The last one is Reactive Security having problems like 9. Filtering and validation at the end to end and 10. The real-time supervising of security. All this aspect can be understood with the help of the diagram given below that explains the big data life cycle.

The validation of input at the endpoint	This is used for the identification of the trustable data. The source for the input data is verified here. There is a question arise when we find the malicious data then how we can filter it for the input?
Privacy preservation with extensible and pasture able properties	The trouble manifestation is defined by enabling security, forward marketing, reducing civil freedom appropriation. The data anonymization is not enough for the management of security. There is provided a search log by AOL but the searchers are able to easily identify the users.
The security in real-time	Here the numbers of alerts generated by the privacy devices are given. This will help to find out the various faults that we simply ignore. The main use of this is for the privacy analysis in the real-time detection of the problems.
Granular audits	The forensics, regulation and compliance use this all security aspects. The missed attacks are an example of this. The data object is deal with the granular audit that are allocated.
The cryptographic control on access and security in communication	The fairness, agreement, authentication in between the distributed entities is ensured by these approaches.
Control of access in a granulated way	Secrecy access for the data that may not be accessed by people. Granulated control of access results in the sharing of data without following the policy of agreement.
Security of the information	The security of big data is a major task seen. Various examples of application like social sites, health sector, anomaly detection etc.the security of information are one of the major issues.
The provenance of the metadata	The complexity of data is increased with the increase in the programming environment of provenance in the applications of the big data. The analysis of this provenance graph for the detection of the dependency of the metadata with respect to the security and confidentiality requires high computations.

We don't find a particular solution for the security and privacy challenges of big data and the security problems that are seen traditionally, those which are generally used to secure a small amount of data are not accurate for the use of the privacy-preserving aspects of big data [18]. We need to understand how to protect the data that is of both types structured and unstructured. Unauthorized access to any data for making changes and for performing malicious activities is one of the major threats to the big data. The basic operation done for doing this task is the encryption of whole data regardless of the storage location of that data. But at the same time, the growing speed of big data and the processing of this data with the encrypted data available becomes somewhere complex.

As per the characteristics seen in the big data, there is a need to do a holistic vision at security aspects [19]. There is a need for surveillance of the data in perspective of the source, type, creator, and the access policy of data. The classification is also must for the critical data identification and to fit that data in the security policy of the organization and applying the policies of the access and handling of data. As a common suggestion the data privacy should be done at the source level and the data itself, so the data security is confirmed at the moment of creation of data, as well the application of data control and prevention mechanisms for the prevention of data leakage and the access control mechanism can be performed at the same time[20].

The security solution for the big data should work with the extension of the security parameters from the enterprise cloud to the public cloud [21]. According to this a mechanism for data provenance also needed to be designed for various domains. Also, in [22] a similar type of mechanism is used to avoid Distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) in the infrastructure of big data. For ensuring privacy, a mechanism for the trustworthiness of the data in the whole lifecycle of big data processing should be there.

In big data, the feature of personalization and the out-coming of this on the user privacy factors as stated in [23]. They stated the issues with respect to EEXCESS, a project aiming to recommend and to provide privacy to the user. Work for the extensions of privacy for UML is presented for helping to understand the requirements of privacy for the applications of big data [24].

When we talk about the big data security and privacy, then it is must to notice the legal requirements for data handling. For the data like Personal Identifiable Information (PII), Intellectual Property (IP), Protected Health Information (PHI), the secure cryptographic mechanism should be there, for the locking and unlocking of data is needed. To do this the mechanism needs to be simple and have a low impact on performance and scalability [25].

As stated earlier traditional mechanisms are not able for solving the problems seen in Big Data. This mechanism can protect static data but when it comes for the computation they don't perform well [26]. So, we need the techniques

that keep data secret while computing specific and targeted data. Some mechanisms are given as Secure Function Evaluation (SFE) [27], Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) [28] and Functional Encryption (FE) [29] can remove the problems of the traditional mechanism of security and privacy.

Homomorphic encryption is one of the encryptions that permits the computations on ciphertext and the results are formed in encrypted form and the decryption gives the results same as on the plain text [30]. Also, there is a Fully Homomorphic Encryption that is useful in different applications [31]. This permits the encryption query on the database, which keeps the secret private user information at the place where the data is stored [31].

3. RESEARCH GAP

Here we have stated the problems that are found in the study done by us for the privacy preservation in big data. Various techniques are involved in this task and are working well for the preservation of privacy. So, there is always a chance for betterment of the previous technology and also the existing techniques face some problems that must be noted and to be worked on. Here are some of the research gaps stated below that we have found in our study:

- The problem is seen that most of the schemes for privacy are designed for the online transaction system.
- The major issue is also related to the veracity of the data, so it needs a different technique for the preservation of privacy related to that particular data.
- The heterogeneity seen in the data that comes under the big data works on a single system for the security aspects and this can not work for the privacy preservation at an extreme level.
- One of the major problems that privacy suffers from is insecure web service. The insecure web service may lead to unauthorized access to the data.
- The small authentication/authorization system also comes under the privacy issues that are seen on the internet.
- The transportation of data between two parties is not encrypted correctly, so lack of encryption in the transport system stands as an issue in privacy preservation.
- Insecure network services come as another issue for the privacy concerns of the data that is transferred on the web.
- The lack of configuration of the system may also become a privacy preservation issue for the big data.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Privacy preservation is one of the major issues seen in big data. The personal data of the user may lead to various threats in cases where the privacy is not preserved. Privacy to the user's data has been on the top most priority in the application of big data. There are various works done on privacy preservation of the big data earlier, and the privacy preservation is achieved at its best. Here we have done a survey on the privacy preservation techniques in big data for the evaluation of the issues and the best methods that are seen for the privacy preservation in big data. The outcome of the survey states that there is a need to design a more secure system for the privacy preservation of data of the users. We also stated the research gaps on which the work should be done. The survey includes various techniques of privacy preservation like cryptography, k-anonymity, etc. The system can be improved by the application of secure methods of privacy preservation.

5. FUTURE WORK

The study done in this paper concludes with the limitations of the techniques seen in the privacy preservation of big data. Various security threats have been observed in our survey and it also gives some ideas for the future implementations in this area. The tasks related to the handling of the variety of data can be improved further, the area of privacy preservation can be increased, more soft and easier cryptographic techniques can be implemented. Also, on the security aspects, the data coming from the source can be secured at the same time if generation so the mechanism for this task could be developed.

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